

MULTISCALE DAMAGE SIMULATION OF CFRP UNDER LOW VELOCITY IMPACTAkinori Yoshimura¹, Masaya Ebina², Yuichiro Aoki³ and Kenichi Sakaue³¹ Department of Aerospace Engineering, Nagoya University
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6-13-1 Osawa, Mitaka, Tokyo 181-0015, Japan**Keywords:** Low velocity impact, Multiscale modelling, Finite element analysis, Damage simulation**ABSTRACT**

The present paper proposes an analysis method for precise prediction of the damage of the CFRP under the low velocity impact event. The method consists of multiple finite element analyses, those belong to two different scales: macro and micro scales, where macroscale corresponds to the 'specimen' scale and microscale corresponds to the 'crack' scale. In the macroscopic scale, the effect of the ply cracks are averaged and modelled by continuum damage mechanics. Delamination is modelled by cohesive element, and fibre damage is modelled by stress criterion and smeared crack model. Microscopic scale model is intended to simulate more precise damage evaluation. A representative unit cell (RUC) of the CFRP laminate is used as a microscopic scale model. In the RUC, the individual ply crack is modelled by cohesive zone model, with delamination modelled by cohesive zone model. Deformation state observed in the each point of the macroscopic model was applied to the RUC for localization analysis, by using key DOF method. Intralaminar cohesive elements were degraded for reproducing matrix crack in the LVI simulation prior to the localization analysis. Matrix crack and delamination predicted by the analyses were qualitatively in good agreement with those in the impacted specimen observed by X-ray CT.

1 INTRODUCTION

CFRP (carbon fibre reinforced plastic) laminate in the aerospace structures might be subjected to low velocity impact (LVI) of foreign objects, such as tool drops. Even if the damage looks minor and harmless from the naked eye, significant damage may occur and the material performance may be severely degraded [1, 2]. Therefore, there is a great demand for high fidelity finite element (FE) model which can be applied for structures made from CFRP [3, 4]. Many studies have been published for proposing the modelling method for LVI event. The models proposed in recent years generally utilize cohesive zone model (CZM) [5, 6] for describing matrix crack, delamination and their correlation [7, 8]. CZM is an efficient method for modelling such discrete damages. However, cohesive zone must be introduced along crack paths prior to the analysis. Thus, crack paths must be known in advance.

A simulation method proposed by the authors in the previous study [9] utilizes continuum damage mechanics (CDM) and smeared crack model (SCM) [10] for describing matrix cracks. This approach does not need the prediction of the crack path in advance. The model simulated projected delamination area of the impacted specimen to be in good agreement with experimental results. However, the delaminations in the lower layers were not precisely predicted because correlation between matrix cracks and delamination was not considered in the model. In the previous model, the effect of the matrix crack is modelled by CDM and SCM through decreasing the stiffness of damaged element. Therefore, stress concentration around matrix crack tip which induces delamination is not able to be described. Consideration of the interaction is needed for more precise LVI simulation.

The present paper proposes an analysis method for precise prediction of the damage of the CFRP under the low velocity impact event. The method consists of multiple finite element analyses, those belong to two different scales: macro and micro scales, where macroscale corresponds to the ‘specimen’ scale and microscale corresponds to the ‘crack’ scale. The model previously proposed by the authors is used as macroscopic model. On the other hand, the induction of delamination by matrix crack is numerically observed by microscopic analysis of a representative unit cell (RUC) model. The induction under various situations can be appropriately observed by localization analyses; implement periodic boundary conditions (PBC) on the RUC model, and apply macroscopic deformation states: strain and curvature predicted by LVI simulation.

This paper is organized as follows: In the second section, procedure of FE analyses is described. Specification of the RUC model and formulation of the PBC are illustrated. In the third section, simulation results are summarized. Finally, conclusions from the present study are reported in the fourth section.

2 METHOD

2.1 Macroscopic Model

As mentioned in the previous section, the modelling strategy proposed in this study consists of two-scale simulation model: macroscopic scale and microscopic scale models. The macroscopic model is for simulation of the behavior of the whole LVI specimen. For the macroscopic model, the model proposed by the authors in the previous study [9] is used. In this subsection, therefore, the modelling method is revisited briefly.

The model consisted of CDM, SCM and CZM. In the model, a CFRP laminate was divided into each lamina, and lamina was divided into continuum shell elements. One shell element represents one lamina in the thickness direction. Fig. 1 shows an overview of the FE model for LVI simulation. The dimensions of the model was 150 mm in length, 100 mm in width. Stacking sequence was $[45/0/90/-45]_{4S}$. Thickness of the model was 6.2 mm. The effect of each damage mode caused by LVI was evaluated by each manner separately, i.e. no interaction of each damage mode was evaluated. Fiber tensile and compressive failure were modeled by SCM and maximum-stress criterion, respectively. Matrix crack was modeled by the enhanced continuum damage mechanics model, which is composed of CDM and SCM. Delamination between laminae was modeled by cohesive contact formulation. Details of the formulation of the macroscopic model can be found in the published paper [9].

Fig. 1: Overview of the macroscopic FE model for LVI simulation.

Fig. 2 shows contour plots of the damage variable of CZM in each interface, corresponding to delamination area predicted in the LVI simulation. Fig. 3 shows tomograms of an impacted specimen of the drop-weight test obtained by X-ray CT. The number indicated in both Figs. 2 and 3 represents the position of the lamina; larger number is closer to the impacted side. As shown in Fig. 2, there was no predicted delamination area in the back side of the impacted laminate. This result is different from the actual delamination area shown in Fig. 3. In the macroscopic model, the correlation between matrix cracks and delamination was not considered. We concluded that the difference was caused by the absence of the correlation.

Fig. 2: Delamination predicted by the macroscopic model

Fig. 3: Tomograms of an impacted specimen of drop-weight test obtained by X-ray CT

2.2 Microscopic Model

Microscopic model is used for the localization simulation, in which damage is modelled more precisely. A representative unit cell (RUC) of the CFRP laminate is used a microscopic scale model. By applying the macroscopic deformation states to the RUC model according to the multiscale calculation technique, more precise damage behavior can be simulated.

Fig. 4 shows an overview of the RUC model. The stacking sequence was the same as the macroscopic model. Each lamina was divided into five solid elements in the thickness direction. Length and width of the RUC were determined to be 0.35 mm by 0.35 mm which was determined according to the matrix crack interval caused by LVI.

In the microscopic model, cohesive elements were employed for describing discrete damages. Fig. 5 shows mesh division of each lamina. Fig. 6 shows position of cohesive elements for describing matrix crack and delamination (hereafter, referred to as intralaminar cohesive elements and interlaminar cohesive elements, respectively).

The 0° and 90° layers, and $\pm 45^\circ$ layers have different mesh so that the intralaminar cohesive elements were placed based on the assumption. Interlaminar cohesive elements were placed between the laminae as shown in Fig. 7. Since the interlaminar cohesive elements and laminae did not have matched meshes, the top and bottom surfaces of the cohesive elements were tied to the laminae by utilizing a surface-based tie constraint (*TIE option in Abaqus). Mesh size of 0° and 90° layers, $\pm 45^\circ$ layers and

interlaminar cohesive elements are 0.025 mm by 0.025 mm, 0.018 mm by 0.018 mm (excluding edges) and 0.010 mm by 0.010 mm, respectively.

The total number of elements was 95,095. For both intralaminar and interlaminar cohesive elements, bilinear traction-separation law is applied. A quadratic stress criterion defines damage initiation. A power law defines damage evolution under mixed mode conditions.

Fig. 4: Overview of the microscopic model.

Fig. 5: Mesh division of each lamina. Intralaminar cohesive elements are highlighted in red.

Fig. 6: Positions of intralaminar cohesive elements (top) and interlaminar cohesive elements (bottom).

2.3 Derivation of Macroscopic Strain and Curvature

In the microscopic model, the periodic boundary condition (PBC) was applied. In this study, the PBC was introduced using key degree of freedom (Key DOF) method proposed by Li et al [11]. The key DOF method provides a remarkably useful function for applying macroscopic strain $E_{\alpha\beta}$ and curvature $K_{\alpha\beta}$ to the RUC, and deriving macroscopic resultant force $N_{\alpha\beta}$ and moment $M_{\alpha\beta}$. For details on the key DOF method, refer to [11] or [12]. In the microscopic model, key DOF method is implemented by using ‘*EQUATION’ function in Abaqus software.

For calculation of the microscopic model, macroscopic strain $E_{\alpha\beta}$ and curvature $K_{\alpha\beta}$ must be applied. In this study, $E_{\alpha\beta}$ and $K_{\alpha\beta}$ were derived from the results of the macroscopic model. First, from the result of macroscopic model, extract Green-Lagrange strain at the maximum impact load from the elements located in the same X-Y coordinates. Then, derive macroscopic strain and curvature from

linear approximation of the strain distribution in the out-of-plane direction. Based on the Kirchhoff-Love's plate theory, in-plane strain is given as

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta} = E_{\alpha\beta} + zK_{\alpha\beta} \quad (1)$$

Note that range of the linear approximation is limited to the lower half of the FE model ($-3.1 \text{ mm} \leq z \leq 0 \text{ mm}$) since the strain distribution did not match the Kirchhoff-Love's plate theory because of the impact damage. Fig. 7 shows an example of deriving macroscopic strain and curvature. According to the result of the linear approximation, $E_{11} = -0.239\%$, $E_{22} = -0.999\%$, $E_{12} = -0.274\%$, $K_{11} = -0.415\%$, $K_{22} = -0.699\%$, $K_{12} = -0.121\%$.

Fig. 7: Example of deriving macroscopic strain and curvature; $x = y = 0$ at maximum impact load

The procedure of localization analysis is as follows: First, extract Green-Lagrange strain and damage variable of matrix cracks from the result of macroscopic simulation, at the position where localization is taken place. Next, derive macroscopic strain and curvature from the Green-Lagrange strain. In addition, parameters of CZM (initial stiffness, maximum traction and fracture toughness) are degraded in order to reproduce matrix cracks predicted in the LVI simulation. Degraded parameters are inversely calculated from the damage variable of matrix cracks based on the constitutive equations of CZM [5]. Then, the macroscopic strain and curvature are applied to the PBC through the key DOFs. Finally, localization analysis is carried out. Table 1 summarizes conditions of localization analysis; positions where localization was taken place, and macroscopic strain and curvature applied to the RUC.

FE analyses were done on the Abaqus/Standard 2016. Table 2 shows the material properties used in the calculations.

Table 1: Positions and Applied Values for Localization Analyses

ID	Position (x, y)	E_{11} [%]	E_{22} [%]	E_{12} [%]	K_{11} [%]	K_{22} [%]	K_{12} [%]
A	(3, 3)	-0.162	-0.293	+0.533	-0.329	-0.432	+0.233
B	(3, -3)	-0.116	-0.392	-0.825	-0.308	-0.509	-0.403

Table 2: Material Properties used in this study

Lamina		Interface	
E_1 [GPa]	152.0	k_n [MPa/mm]	1.0×10^7
E_2 [GPa]	8.000	k_s [MPa/mm]	1.0×10^7
E_3 [GPa]	8.000	k_t [MPa/mm]	1.0×10^7
ν_{12}	0.34	t_n [MPa]	66.9
ν_{13}	0.34	t_s [MPa]	100
ν_{23}	0.45	t_t [MPa]	100
G_{12} [GPa]	4.030	G_{IC} [(N · mm)/mm ²]	0.54
G_{13} [GPa]	4.030	G_{IIC} [(N · mm)/mm ²]	1.64
G_{23} [GPa]	4.030	G_{IIIC} [(N · mm)/mm ²]	1.64

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Fig. 2, positions where localization was taken place are indicated by points with the ID in Table 1. Figs. 8 and 9 show the contour plots of damage variables of intralaminar and interlaminar cohesive elements, corresponding to predicted matrix cracks and delamination, respectively.

Matrix cracks and delamination predicted by the analyses were qualitatively in good agreement with those in the impacted specimen observed by X-ray CT. For example, in point B (Fig. 9), the position of delaminated interfaces in the upper half of the laminate was precisely captured. In addition, the induction of delamination by progress of matrix cracks was observed not only in the upper layer but also in the lower layer of the RUC. Therefore, it can be expected that the interaction between matrix cracks and delamination will be derived numerically.

However, delamination is still slightly underestimated, especially at the point A (Fig. 8). We concluded that the cause of this underestimation is the disregard for strain history in LVI event. In the localization analysis, applied macroscopic strain and curvature increases linearly to those at maximum impact load. This is decisively different from the strain history in LVI event. As a result, the path dependence of damage evolution might be overlooked.

In addition, the method of deriving macroscopic strain and curvature might be the cause of underestimation in the upper half of the RUC. Strain distribution in the upper half of the FE model in LVI simulation was neglected when deriving macroscopic strain and curvature. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 7, strain applied to the upper half of the RUC model is less than that in the LVI simulation. Thus, delamination in the upper half of the RUC was underestimated. Review of the method of deriving macroscopic strain and curvature to be applied to the RUC is needed.

Fig. 8: Result of localization analysis at point A ($x = 3, y = 3$)

Fig. 9: Result of localization analysis at point A ($x = 3, y = -3$)

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, an analysis method for precise prediction of the damage of the CFRP under the low velocity impact event was proposed. The method consists of multiple finite element analyses, those belong to two different scales: macro and micro scales. For macroscopic analysis, the model the authors previously proposed was used. On the other hand, RUC of the CFRP laminate was used for microscopic model, in which matrix crack and delamination were modeled using cohesive zone model. In the macroscopic model, the interaction between matrix crack and delamination was not considered, whereas it was considered in the microscopic model. Macroscopic strain and curvature were derived from the results of the macroscopic model, and they are applied to the microscopic model by using key DOF method. Matrix cracks and delamination predicted by the analyses were qualitatively in good agreement with those in the impacted specimen observed by X-ray CT. The induction of delamination by progress of matrix cracks was observed not only in the upper layer but also in the lower layer of the RUC. Therefore, it can be expected that the interaction between matrix cracks and delamination will be derived numerically.

In future studies, we will derive the interaction by utilizing the RUC model and the method of localization analysis proposed in this paper. Subsequently, we will implement the interaction in our previous model for more advanced low velocity impact simulation.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M.O.W. Richardson, M.J. Wisheart, Review of low-velocity impact properties of composite materials. *Compos. Part A*, **27(12A)**, 1996, pp. 1123-1133.
- [2] G.A.O Davies, R. Olsson, Impact on composite structures. *Aeronaut J.*, **108(1089)**, 2004, pp. 541-563.
- [3] B. N. Cox, Q. Yang, In quest of virtual tests for structural composites. *Science* **314(5802)**, 2006, pp. 1102-1107.
- [4] M.R. Abir, T.E. Tay, M. Ridha, H.P. Lee, Modelling damage growth in composites subjected to impact and compression after impact. *Compos. Struct.*, **168**, 2017, pp. 13-25.
- [5] P.P. Camanho, C.G. Davila, Mixed-mode decohesion finite elements for the simulation of delamination in composite materials. NASA/TM-2002-211737, 2002, pp. 1-37.
- [6] M.R. Wisnom, Modelling discrete failures in composites with interface elements. *Compos. A*, **41(7)**, 2010, pp. 795-805.
- [7] C. Bouvet, B. Castanié, M. Bizeul, J. Barrau, Low velocity impact modelling in laminate composite panels with discrete interface elements. *Int. J. Solids Struct.* **46(14-15)**, 2009, pp. 2809-2821.
- [8] X.C. Sun, M.R. Wisnom, S.R. Hallett, Interaction of inter- and intralaminar damage in scaled quasi-static indentation tests: Part 2 - Numerical simulation. *Compos. Struct.*, **136**, 2016, pp. 727-742.

- [9] M. Ebina, A. Yoshimura, K. Sakaue, A.M. Waas, High fidelity simulation of low velocity impact behavior of CFRP laminate. *Compos. A*, **113**, 2018, pp. 166-179
- [10] C. Heinrich, A.M. Waas, Investigation of progressive damage and fracture in laminated composites using the smeared crack approach. *Comput. Mater. Continua*. **35(2)**, 2013, pp.155-181.
- [11] S. Li, N. Warrior, Z. Zou, F. Almaskari, A unit cell for FE analysis of materials with the microstructure of a staggered pattern. *Compos. A*, **42(7)**, 2011, pp. 801-811.
- [12] K. Yoshida, M. Nakagami, Numerical analysis of bending and transverse shear properties of plain-weave fabric composite laminates considering intralaminar inhomogeneity. *Adv. Compos. Mater.*, **26(2)**, 2017, pp. 135-156.